

UTILIZING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE EDUCATION OF GIFTED CHILDREN: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

Incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) tools into the education of gifted children can offer new and exciting opportunities for both teachers and students. By embracing these tools and learning how to use them effectively, we can prepare gifted children for future challenges and help them stay ahead of the curve. This paper discusses the challenges and prospects of integrating artificial intelligence into the education of gifted children. The paper views gifted children as those who possess advanced intellectual abilities when compared to their peers. It also discusses the concept of artificial intelligence and notes that artificial intelligence offers significant potential in gifted education by providing personalized learning experiences, advanced content access, and opportunities for enhanced skills development. However, challenges such as stable power supply, and high cost of maintenance among other factors were discussed. The paper concluded by encouraging the integration of this technology in gifted education to enable these students to cope with future challenges in society.

Introduction

Technological breakthroughs in the last decade have greatly changed classroom practices globally. Artificial intelligence (AI) has been one of the key factors that drive the learning space in recent times. Artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science dedicated to creating intelligent systems that can perform activities that require human thought in most situations, such as decision-making, learning, and reasoning (Alam, 2022). According to Akgun and Greenhow (2021), artificial intelligence offers personalized instruction in the learning situation, mechanizes the delivery of feedback and tests, and enables the identification of the learners' strengths and weaknesses. The significance of understanding the potential of AI in the education system cannot be overstated. It is imperative for both students and educators to gain a comprehensive understanding of the impacts of AI, particularly as it becomes increasingly integrated into various facets of life (Makarenko, Borysenko, Horokhivska, Kozub, and Yaremenko, 2024).

The growing prevalence of AI has prompted considerable interest in the education sector due to its capacity to potentially transform the teaching and learning processes. The incorporation of AI into education has sparked new concepts and avenues for educational reforms, precipitating changes in educational paradigms, therefore giving rise to innovative products such as smart teaching and smart classrooms (Zhu, 2024). Researchers have also highlighted the possibilities offered by AI in education, emphasizing the potential for improved educational outcomes, enhanced knowledge retention, and personalized learning experiences (Chen, Chen, and Lin, 2020; Hua, 2022; Jaiswal and Arun, 2021; Zawacki-Richter, Martin, Bond, and Gouveneur, 2019). On the other hand, Satir (2023) opines that the implementation of AI technologies tailored to individual needs has the potential to enhance students' engagement and motivation. It has also been seen as a means to automate administrative tasks, facilitate customized learning experiences, leverage smart data for teaching, and enhance student support (Hinojo-Lucena, Diaz, Reche, and Rodriguez, 2019).

Gifted children have superior intellectual abilities when compared to those of the same age. They are known for their abstract and analytical thinking skills. They tend to be more sensitive to technological advancements and are inclined to critically analyze these developments (Renzulli, 2012). Often, their unique perspectives on innovations and complex issues enhance their potentials to comprehend societal advancement.

Price and Milgram (1993) note that gifted children require differentiated educational programmes and services beyond those normally provided by regular schools in order for them to fully realize their potential. Since gifted children often have specific learning qualities and abilities, they require different approaches to fulfil these potentials. Artificial intelligence platforms can personalize the learning environment for gifted children, providing them with advanced content based on their skills, creating individualized plans that allow for the acceleration of knowledge acquisition and providing timely feedback that facilitates the tailoring of instruction as appropriate (Akgun and Greenhow, 2021). Ye (2023) asserts that the strategic incorporation of AI into the education of gifted students will not only improve learning outcomes but also foster an inclusive environment that supports the development of each student's unique

abilities. Therefore, it is pertinent for teachers to explore ways of using this technology to enhance learning in modern-day classrooms.

Conceptual Discourse

Artificial Intelligence

The term artificial intelligence is one of the trending concepts in contemporary literature. In other words, artificial intelligence is a subject matter that scholars in diverse fields are currently trying to harness its importance and applicability (Gbaden, Gambo, and Shem, 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) is a domain of computer science, which deals with the development of intelligent computer systems that are capable of perceiving, analyzing, and reacting accordingly to inputs. AI software is designed to mimic human behaviours to assist humans for better performance in the fields of science and technology. In the education sector, AI simulates human learning, comprehension, problem-solving, decision-making, creativity and autonomy. EL-Hadi (2023) notes that “there is no universally agreed definition of AI. Different authors define the concept based on their perspectives. For example, *OECD* (2016) defines AI as the ability of machine systems to acquire and apply knowledge, and to carry out intelligent behaviours. This includes a variety of cognitive tasks (such as sensing, processing oral languages, reasoning, learning, and making decisions), and the ability to move and manipulate objects accordingly.

Similarly, Russell and Norvig (2010) conceive of artificial intelligence as the design of a rational agent that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chance of success. They classify other definitions of AI into a two-by-two matrix: Thinking versus acting; and (Thinking or Acting) human versus rational. Common points of view in these definitions are that artificial intelligence is technology-driven. Also, they are created to perform some tasks that humans are meant to undertake. *Wiktionary* (2014) views AI as a branch of computer science dealing with the reproduction or mimicking of human-level intelligence, self-awareness, knowledge, conscience, and thoughts in computer programs. According to Barr and Feigenbaum (1981), AI is the part of computer science concerned with designing intelligent computer systems, that is, systems that exhibit the characteristics associated with intelligence in human behaviour, understanding, language, learning, reasoning, solving problems, and the like.

Giftedness

Defining giftedness is complicated and challenging. According to Kaufman and Sternberg (2008), giftedness is a label that can be applied to different criteria, variously perceived as general, spanning the numerous domains, or as specific pertaining to certain areas. Giftedness is historically transient with some culturally specific connotations. Initial efforts to define giftedness date to Terman and Hollingwroth (1926), who concentrated mainly on IQ tests (Ivarsson, 2023). Passow’s theory that defined intelligence as the tool for success in the socially valued areas, is emphasized by Turkman (2020) but not all fields are mentioned as only the socially valued areas, such as languages, social sciences, natural sciences, and mathematics, are listed. Turkman (2020) characterizes gifted children as those who have demonstrated high ability

in areas such as general intellectual ability, specific academic aptitude, creative thinking, leadership, visual and performing arts, and psychomotor ability.

In 1972, the US Office of Education defined the gifted as students demonstrating high ability in one or more areas including general intellectual ability, specific academic aptitude, creative thinking, leadership, visual and performing arts, and psychomotor ability. Renzulli (1978) also proposed the Three-Ring conception of giftedness, suggesting that high potential arises from the interaction of three clusters of traits above average abilities, high task commitment, and creativity (Renzulli, 2006). General abilities include abstract thinking, sophisticated reasoning, keen spatial relations, and verbal fluency. Renzulli argues that the general traits are supported by specific abilities that allow knowledge to be applied in problem-solving. He further pointed out that task commitment combines interests, motivation, perseverance, openness to criticism, and self confidence. The third cluster centred on creativity, which is a key indicator of potential measured by fluency, flexibility, originality, curiosity, and openness to new experiences. In 1999, Gagne introduced another perspective by putting a difference between innate potential (giftedness and developed ability (talent) (Ivarson, 2023). In this development, he stressed the interpersonal and environmental factors and suggested that about 10% of the population could be called gifted. He further explained that gifts become talents through learning.

In the United States of America, the National Association for Gifted Children (NAGC) defines gifted children as those students who demonstrate outstanding aptitude or competence in one or more areas, with an exceptional ability to reason and learn, or have a documented performance that is among the top 10% in one or more domains (Turkman, 2020). However, Worrell, Subotnik, Olszewki-Kubilius, and Dixson (2019) explained that giftedness is a developmental process characterized as potential achievement and eminence in which cognitive and psychological variables are of paramount importance in its evolution. In consideration of all these concepts, this paper adopts a multiple-dimension approach that brings Gagne's concept into Renzulli's model of the Three-Ring conception of giftedness, submitting that giftedness is a combination of innate abilities and environmental influencing factors.

Learning Styles of Gifted Children

Learning is described as a permanent change in behaviour occurring as a result of repetition or experience (Erkus, 1994). Learning is associated with physiological, biological, and social variables. One of the variables related to learning is learning styles. Learning style is a common way or pattern of behaviour that people use in acquiring knowledge. It is an individual's natural and habitual pattern of acquiring and processing information in a learning situation (Hooda and Devi, 2017). Mackerachen (2004) describes learning style as the cognitive, affective, social, and physiological behaviour that serves as a relatively stable indicator of how learners perceive, interact with, and respond to the learning environment.

Gifted children display different learning styles. They prefer learning in a variety of activities such as games, and independent studies through problem-solving, memorization, and lecturing (Stewart, 1981). Establishing a comprehensive conceptualization will enable educators to take into account the learning styles and strategies of each child to get important information

about the approach and resources required for the development of a child. Having highly advanced perceptual characteristics, the gifted student can use more than one learning style at the same time. Gifted children can perform a high degree of learning with auditory, visual, and kinaesthetic learning styles (Price and Milgram, 1993). Altun and Yazici (2010) noted that gifted students prefer to use visual and kinaesthetic learning styles more than their non-gifted peers. Gifted students tend to be more independent in their learning and depend on self-motivators, rather than exterior ones, and they also like to take part (being active) in the learning process (Pyryt, 1998).

The gifted student are kinaesthetic and better group learners than normal students and also more willing to express themselves in writing rather than orally (Hooda and Devi, 2017). They are more likely to be encouraged to learn when the teacher employs hands-on activities that enable them to maximize their potentials. Gifted children have the need to be more interactive in their classrooms where the teacher notes and responds to their preferences, hence motivating them to achieve better results. Gifted children are better group learners than the non-gifted students, and also more willing to express themselves in writing. According to Chan (2001) gifted children show preference for learning styles related to discussions and independent learning, and at a younger age, they show a greater preference for learning styles related to structured activities and games than the older age group.

Implications of Learning Styles

Any attempt made towards identifying the learning styles of gifted students will help the teacher in developing suitable methods for the teaching process. Hein and Buday (2000) found that when the learning environment is designed to accommodate the learning styles of the individuals, their achievement increased. Tomlinson, Brighton, Hertberg, Callahan, Moon, Brimijoin, and Reynolds (2003) also argued that knowing students preferred learning styles can help teachers differentiate the curriculum and services, leading to improved academic, and attitude gains. Lamarch-Bisson (2002) claimed that learning style differences affect “how we learn, how we solve problems, how we work, how we participate in different activities, how we react in a group, and how we relate to others around us”, noting that most gifted children have a dominant learning style, but students who understand their pertinent strengths and weaknesses can learn to adapt when needing a different learning style. Self-aware students can also work to improve non-preferred styles, potentially increasing their achievement in courses that do not fit well with their dominant learning style (Hooda and Devi, 2017). Understanding these learning styles will enable the facilitator to arrange the learning environment with suitable artificial intelligence gadgets that cater to the needs of diverse groups of gifted students.

Challenges to the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence Technology in Education

Mentor (2025) submitted that along with the potential benefits of artificial intelligence come some difficult challenges and risks that the education community must navigate. Some of these challenges are discussed below:

- 1. Overreliance on Technology:** Both teachers and students face the risk of overreliance on AI-driven technology. For students, this can hinder learning, especially the development

of critical thinking. This challenge can also extend to educators. It is therefore important to note that while AI can speed up lesson plan generation, speed does not equal quality.

2. **Privacy Concerns:** When students or educators interact with AI-powered tools, their conversations and personal information can be stored and analyzed, posing a risk to their privacy. With public AI systems, educators should refrain from entering or exposing sensitive details about themselves, their colleagues, or their students, including but not limited to private communications, personally identifiable information, health data, academic performance, emotional well-being, and financial records.
3. **Equity Issues:** Not all students have equal access to computing devices and the internet. This imbalance can accelerate a widening achievement gap between students from different socioeconomic backgrounds.
4. **Funding:** Implementing and launching AI technology need substantial financial resources. AI innovation faces significant obstacles due to financial restrictions in many countries, especially in developing nations like Nigeria. Investment in AI research and development is insufficient. Adeniran (2024) noted that obtaining financial assistance is crucial for constructing the necessary infrastructure, procuring cutting-edge technology, and cultivating the human resources required for AI.
5. **Promotion of Public Knowledge and Approval:** The effective adoption of AI technology relies heavily on the crucial factors of public knowledge and acceptance. AI implementation may be hindered by misconceptions and anxieties including worries about job loss. It is imperative to enhance public knowledge through educational initiatives and outreach activities to foster confidence and embrace AI technology.
6. **Unstable Power Supply:** One of the fundamental barriers to the adoption of AI technologies in the education system is erratic power supply. The consistent power supply is critical for effectively powering the AI applications that are becoming increasingly essential in modern classrooms. AI relies heavily on computational processes, and frequent power outages may disrupt the seamless operation of AI tools, making them unreliable in the classroom.
7. **Infrastructure Decay:** The dearth of adequate infrastructure to support the integration of AI into classrooms is another major challenge. AI systems require substantial computing power, storage, and network capabilities. Without the necessary infrastructure, implementing AI tools in the education system becomes a daunting task.
8. **Ethical and Regulatory Consideration:** Adeniran (2024) notes that the use of AI technology gives rise to a multitude of ethical and legal concerns that necessitate attention to guarantee responsible and equitable utilization. Primary issues are data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the possibility of employment displacement. The lack of a strong legal and ethical framework to regulate the research and implementation of artificial intelligence can pose a serious challenge to the integration of AI into the education system.

Prospects of Integrating Artificial Intelligence in the Education of Gifted Children

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has emerged as a transformative force globally, offering innovative solutions to enhance learning outcomes and address educational disparities. The following discussion presents the prospect of integrating artificial intelligence in the education of gifted children.

Personalized Learning: One of the key applications of AI in education of the gifted children is personalized learning which tailors educational content and instructional methods to meet the individual needs and learning styles of students. Adaptive learning systems powered by AI algorithms can analyze students' performance data, identify strengths and weaknesses and dynamically adjust learning materials and activities accordingly (Chen et al, 2020). This approach enables gifted children to learn at their own pace, fostering deeper understanding and mastery of concepts.

Intelligent Tutoring Systems: AI-based intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) represent another promising application of AI in gifted education. These systems leverage machine learning algorithms to simulate one-on-one tutoring interactions, providing personalized guidance and feedback to students (VanLehn, 2011). ITS can assess students' understanding in real time, diagnose misconceptions, and deliver adaptive instruction to address learning gaps.

Data-Driven Decision Making: AI enables data-driven decision making in gifted education by analyzing vast amount of educational data to identify trends, patterns, and areas for improvement. Through techniques such as predictive analytics and data mining, AI can generate actionable insights to inform curriculum development, instructional design and policy formulation (Romero and Ventura, 2010). By leveraging data analytics, education stakeholders can make evidence-based decisions to optimize resource allocation and enhance educational outcomes.

Advanced Content and Resources: AI can provide access to a vast array of advanced learning materials, research tools and opportunities for exploration beyond the standard curriculum. In this capacity, AI aids the acceleration of content for gifted children.

Skill Development: AI can support the development of crucial skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, creativity and research through interactive simulations, personalized challenges and AI powered feedback.

Increased Engagement: AI powered tools, like interactive games and simulations, can make learning more engaging and motivating for gifted students.

Enhanced Critical Thinking and Problem Solving: AI powered tools can offer challenging scenarios, simulations and personalized feedback to foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills in gifted students.

Collaboration: Artificial intelligence has the capacity to foster collaboration among gifted children by providing them with the platform to interact and share ideas, especially for those who share similar interests. It can also link gifted students with their mentors or teachers for professional advice.

Conclusion

The education system is expected to go through a great change in the future by implementing new technologies and artificial intelligence-based systems in order to improve the quality of education. Some of these innovations could benefit gifted children whose talent is often disregarded in the traditional educational setting. Due to AI, gifted students in the future might use Personalized Learning Systems (IPICS) that adapt to each student individually, and other generative AI in order to receive feedback or help that cannot be provided by every human teacher. It is important to note that the AI innovation does not go without challenges. These challenges include the ability to secure a stable power supply, availability of infrastructure to back up the platforms, high cost of installation, and maintenance of the gadgets. Despite these challenges, artificial intelligence has the capacity to enhance the education of gifted children in many ways, including personalized learning and intelligent tutoring systems. Therefore, every attempt should be made to provide gifted children with this opportunity as it will lead to improved academic outcomes.

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